

An Evaluation of the Development Process of Bureaucracy in the Republic of Türkiye Between 1923 and 1982

1923- 1982 Yılları Arasında Türkiye Cumhuriyeti'nde Bürokrasinin Gelişim Süreci Üzerine Bir Değerlendirme

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ABSTRACT

The newly established Republic of Türkiye serves as a good example of how bureaucracy can become one of the founding elements within the state structure. The republican bureaucracy achieved a position of supremacy through institutions and mechanisms established throughout the country during the 1923-1946 period, thereby ensuring the integration of the party and the state and eliminating the boundaries between politics and bureaucracy. In the 1946-1960 period, following the establishment of the republic, the bureaucracy's loss of power, which began with World War II, reached its peak with the Democratic Party, composed mostly of members who had been pushed out of the system, coming to power in 1950. During the period 1960-1982, the civilian bureaucracy, due to the feelings of exclusion it experienced, acted in concert with the military bureaucracy and played an influential role in the execution of the 1960 military coup. This study attempts to examine the transformation undergone by the bureaucracy in the Republic of Türkiye between 1923 and 1982 in terms of its status, economy, society, and law through its relationship with the government. In this context, the factors that led to this transformation are presented from a historical and administrative perspective.

Anahtar Kavramlar: *Bureaucracy, Status of Bureaucrats, Development of Bureaucracy in the Republic of Türkiye, Bureaucracy in the Single-Party Period, Bureaucracy in Multi-Party Political Life..*

ÖZET

Bürokrasinindevlet yapılanması içerisinde kurucu unsurlardan birisi haline gelmesinigöstermesi açısından yeni kurulan Türkiye Cumhuriyeti iyi bir örnek teşkil etmektedir. Cumhuriyet bürokrasisi, 1923- 1946 Döneminde ülkenin her köşesine ve alanına sirayet edecek biçimde oluşturulan kurumlar ve mekanizmalarla tekçil bir konum elde ederek parti- devlet bütünleşmesini sağlayarak siyaset ve bürokrasi arasındaki sınırları ortadan kaldırmıştır. 1946- 1960 Döneminde cumhuriyetin kuruluşunun ardından çoğunluğu sistemin dışına itilen mensuplardan meydana gelen Demokrat Parti'nin 1950 yılında iktidara gelmesiyle birlikte bürokrasinin II. Dünya Savaşı ile başlayan güç kaybı zirve noktaya ulaşmıştır. 1960- 1982 Döneminde ise sivil bürokrasi yaşamış olduğu dışlanmışlık nedeniyle askeri bürokrasi ile birlikte hareket ederek 1960 askeri darbesinin gerçekleştirilmesinde etkili olmuştur. Bu çalışma kapsamında, 1923- 1982 yılları arasında Türkiye Cumhuriyeti'nde bürokrasinin iktidar ile ilişkileri üzerinden statüsel, ekonomik, sosyal ve hukuki açılarından geçirdiği dönüşüm ele alınmaya çalışılmıştır. Bu çerçevede ise, söz konusu dönüşüme yol açan etmenler tarihsel ve idari açıdan ortaya konmuştur.

Keywords: *Bürokrasi, Bürokratların Statüsü, Türkiye Cumhuriyeti'nde Bürokrasinin Gelişimi, Tek Parti Döneminde Bürokrasi, Çok Partili Siyasi Hayatta Bürokrasi.*

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INTRODUCTION

The newly established Republic of Türkiye was founded on the remnants of the Ottoman Empire rather than rejecting the existing state tradition. In this context, the founders of the new republic and the military and civil bureaucrats of the late Ottoman Empire began a series of revolutions after the national struggle. During the period between 1923 and 1946, these bureaucrats became the sole defenders of Atatürk's principles, holding the power of the state and achieving a prestigious status. During this period, the integration of the republic's founding party and the state was fully achieved in 1936 when the Minister of the Interior, the General Secretary of the Republican People's Party, and the governors also became the provincial chairmen of the party. Ultimately, during the Single Party Period, bureaucrats consolidated their power through state-oriented policies, economic initiatives, and the integration of the party and the state.

Between 1946 and 1960, democracy in Türkiye transitioned to a multi-party system, a period during which bureaucrats lost the power they had acquired. During this period, the Democratic Party, which came to power, attempted to remove the bureaucracy from power and make it dependent on itself. During this period, a series of reform efforts involving the bureaucracy were carried out based on reports prepared by experts such as Neumark, Barker, and Martin Cush, but the desired results were not achieved. In the process leading up to the 1960 coup, the civilian and military bureaucracy, which had lost power, joined forces with the military and played an active role. Following the coup, bureaucrats received compensation for their support of the military through institutions such as the State Planning Organisation, which was established alongside institutions such as the Constitutional Court and the National Security Council, which were granted constitutional status in the 1961 the Constitution of the Turkish Republic. Between 1960 and 1982, the Civil Servants Law No. 657 was enacted, introducing more comprehensive and status-based regulations than the Civil Servants Law enacted in 1926. Additionally, during this period, due to the increasing number of coalition governments, bureaucratic employment became a means of finding work based on political patronage, in line with unemployment.

In this study, the bureaucratic development process in the Republic of Türkiye between 1923 and 1982 is examined within the framework of Weberian bureaucracy. Within this framework, Max Weber's understanding of bureaucracy is first briefly explained, followed by an examination of the development of bureaucracy in the Republic of Türkiye during the Single Party Period (1923-1946), the Multi-Party Period (1946-1960), and the Period Between 1960 and 1982.

1. LITERATURE

The issue of bureaucracy in Türkiye has long been one of the important topics addressed in both political science and public administration. With the founding of the republic, numerous academic studies have been conducted on the structure of bureaucracy, its modes of operation, and its relationship with politics. Most of these studies have evaluated the Turkish example within the framework of Weber's understanding of bureaucracy. On the other hand, there are also studies that address the transformation of bureaucracy over time from a historical and institutional perspective.

However, a notable shortcoming is that this literature generally highlights specific periods or individual events. There are very few comprehensive assessments that address the period from 1923 to 1982 as a whole. This study steps in at this point, aiming to compile and analyze the existing literature and present a general framework of the early period of Turkish bureaucracy.

1.1. Max Weber's Understanding of Bureaucracy

The word bureaucracy is derived from the words 'burra' (dark-coloured fabric spread over tables) and 'kratos' (sovereignty, administration) and is a concept that basically refers to the administration being carried out by civil servants working in offices. In this context, bureaucracy carries the meaning of 'the rule of offices' (Özer, 2005:26).

Max Weber (1864–1920) is considered one of the founders of modern social sciences and is inseparable from the concept of bureaucracy (Bahçeci and Demirci, 2022: 676). Max Weber made significant contributions to management sciences with his theory of bureaucracy, which he developed in order to understand the functioning of modern societies. According to Weber, bureaucracy is the most rational form of administration based on 'legal-rational' authority (Weber, 1978: 217). The main characteristics of bureaucratic organisations include hierarchical structure, specialisation, written rules, and task-based relationships.

Weber's bureaucratic model was developed to increase organisational efficiency in modern capitalist societies. Bureaucracy is a preferred structure, especially in large-scale public institutions, due to its 'technical superiority' (Gerth and Mills, 1958: 214). In this context, Weber's approach is accepted as a fundamental source for understanding how organisations are structured and how they operate through rational rules. However, contemporary literature addresses both the strengths and limitations of Weberian bureaucracy. For example, Du Gay (2000: 17) emphasises the ethical responsibility Weber attributes to bureaucracy, arguing that bureaucracy is not merely a mechanical structure but also a system with normative values. Similarly, Albrow (1970: 69) states that Weber's model is an ideal type and that bureaucratic organisations in the real world do not fully conform to this model.

Another area where bureaucracy is criticised is organisational flexibility and innovation capacity. Heady (2001: 145) emphasises that the rigid structure of Weberian bureaucracy, particularly in developing countries, complicates reform processes. Peters (2010: 88) argues that bureaucracy must be transformed in response to changing public administration paradigms (such as new public management).

Furthermore, Weber's approach to 'rationalisation' positions bureaucracy as a result of modernity. Collins (1986: 58), in explaining Weber's concept of rationalisation, states that bureaucracy is a structure guided by objective rules, rather than personal decisions. However, there are also criticisms that this rationalisation restricts individual creativity (Kaufman, 1977: 21). In today's public administration, Weberian models have been replaced by 'post-bureaucratic' structures. Grey (2005: 112) emphasises that post-bureaucratic models offer more flexible, horizontal and

participatory forms of organisation, but that these structures may lack the accountability provided by Weberian principles.

Weber's theory of bureaucracy is an ideal model developed by examining the institutional structures of the time in order to respond to the needs of industrial society. This model reflects an approach based on legal-rational authority as opposed to patrimonial authority. Indeed, this understanding of bureaucracy has been functional in meeting the needs of industrial society and continues to maintain its validity and influence today. As a result, bureaucracy stands out as the most widespread, effective, and dominant form of organisation in the regulation and efficient conduct of social life, as no alternative structure has yet been developed (Akçakaya, 2016: 293-294).

2. METHOD

This study is a literature review aimed at understanding the transformations undergone by the bureaucracy of the Republic of Türkiye between 1923 and 1982. No fieldwork or archival research was conducted; instead, an assessment was made based on previous academic studies, books, articles, theses, and documents shedding light on the period.

The main objective of the study is to understand how the bureaucracy in Türkiye developed from its establishment to 1982 the Constitution of the Turkish Republic and to reveal the political, social, and institutional dynamics behind this process. In this context, approaches such as Weber's understanding of bureaucracy and historical institutionalism provided the theoretical basis for the evaluation process.

Throughout the study, the impact of legal regulations, constitutional amendments, and political developments from various periods on the bureaucratic structure has been examined, and prominent views in the academic literature have been addressed comparatively. Both classical sources and current academic studies were utilized in the literature review.

In this respect, the study aims to bring together existing knowledge and rethink the approximately sixty-year evolution of the Turkish bureaucracy from a systematic and holistic perspective.

3. ANALYSIS RESULTS

3.1. The Development of Bureaucracy in The Republic of Türkiye (1923-1982)

This section will examine the development of bureaucracy in the Republic of Türkiye through the lens of the Single-Party Period (1923-1946), the Multi-Party Period (1946-1960) and the period between 1960 and 1982.

3.1.1. The Single-Party Period (1923-1946)

The establishment of the Republic of Türkiye was shaped not so much by the direct destruction of the institutions of the Ottoman Empire but rather by the Western-oriented modernisation movements that had been ongoing since the Tanzimat Period (Üstündağ and Bilgin, 2026: 42). In this

context, while the republican administration continued its modernisation efforts in the economic, political and social spheres, it was forced to establish the state structure on the existing administrative system of the Ottoman Empire.

Indeed, the founding cadres of the republic played key roles at turning points during the collapse of the Ottoman Empire and sought to introduce innovations by reflecting on the mistakes made during this process. In this context, 93% of the military academy graduates and 85% of the civil service graduates who were part of the Ottoman Empire continued their duties in the newly established Republic of Türkiye (Göküş, 2000: 24).

Under the leadership of Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, the Ottoman monarchy was abolished on 1 November 1922, and the republican regime was declared on 29 October 1923. This political transformation was institutionalised with the 1924 the Constitution of the Turkish Republic, and the foundations of a secular state structure were laid. This constitution, like the one inherited from the Ottoman Empire, shaped the young Republic of Türkiye, which was trying to establish a new state structure, on the basis of centralism (Özer and Üstündağ, 2025: 431). As part of constitutional reforms, madrasas were closed, religious titles and Ottoman titles were abolished, and religious-based structures were separated from the state system (Lewis, 1961: 45). Regulations such as the 1925 Hat Law, the abolition of religious orders, and the Surname Law aimed to enable the people to acquire a new civic identity in the public sphere (Yılmaz, 2014: 439). At the same time, public administration was restructured, and the bureaucratic structure was strengthened in line with a centralised approach (Javits, 1961: 82).

From a bureaucratic perspective, some negative traditions related to public administration, such as centralisation, as well as the positive and negative attitudes, behavioural patterns and values of the Ottoman bureaucracy, were also inherited. Following the successful outcome of the national struggle, the civil and military bureaucracy launched a revolutionary movement for the people and oriented towards the people (Yalçındağ, 1970: 55). It should also be noted that during this period, the bureaucracy held a fundamental guiding position in the country's administration and even had absolute sovereignty, and that there was a continuity between this period and the preceding Ottoman period. During the Single Party Period, the bureaucracy emerged with distinct characteristics during the Ottoman Empire and attempted to implement the idea of governing the state within the framework of Western-oriented reforms by establishing a modern nation state in the early days of the republic (Akın, 2011: 85).

The bureaucracy in the early years of the republic was shaped by two fundamental ideas: first, to continue developing the reforms that had been implemented, to root out corruption, and to preserve the reforms; and second, to lead economic development. In addition, the statist policies that were implemented enabled the bureaucracy to intervene in society. For this reason, the bureaucracy was granted broad powers and legal safeguards (Eryılmaz, 2012: 295). Firstly, following the establishment of the republic, a law was enacted on 1 October 1922 with the aim of purging officials who had previously supported the Istanbul Government and the monarchy. Under this law, all state officials

were temporarily deemed unemployed, and a new cadre of officials for the republic was formed (Güllü, 2017: 122).

Article 23 of the 1924 the Constitution of the Turkish Republic states that civil service and membership of parliament cannot be held concurrently, while Article 93 states that “the qualifications, rights, duties, salaries and allowances of civil servants, their appointment and dismissal, and their promotion and advancement” shall be regulated by a special law, thus providing civil servants with constitutional protection from the very beginning of the republic. In 1928, the Arabic alphabet was replaced by the Latin alphabet (Salehi, 2020: 14), and in 1929, Law No. 1452 was enacted for civil servants and Law No. 1453 for military personnel (Öktem, 1992: 87). Between 1932 and 1938, language purification policies were implemented under the leadership of the Turkish Language Association (Kreiser, 1992: 200).

The Civil Servants Law No. 788, enacted in 1926, is significant as it was the first regulation concerning the rights of civil servants during the republican period. This regulation established the career system for civil servants, principles for passing examinations and promotion within the profession, and also regarded them as agents of the state.

However, classification was not accepted in the regulation in question (Göküş, 2000: 27). Furthermore, Law No. 3656 on the Unification and Adjustment of Civil Servants' Salaries, enacted in 1939, determined the basic elements of civil servants' salaries. However, during the Single Party Period, the status of civil servants was quite high. Both their pioneering activities during the War of Independence and their role in defending Atatürk's principles by holding power in the republic led to the bureaucracy gaining power and prestige. Another factor influencing this situation was that there were no other career options for people with high status in society who had received a secular and Western education, which increased their prestige. Additionally, during this period, the classes that now held property (the bourgeoisie, the elite, etc.) also began to compete for top positions in the bureaucracy (Şaylan, 1986: 75, cited in Göküş, 2000: 26).

In the early days of the republic, the bureaucracy, whose scope of responsibility was extremely limited, did not yet have comprehensive social and economic responsibilities. Therefore, it operated through ministries that performed more traditional public duties, such as ‘internal affairs, foreign affairs, finance, justice, and defence,’ and ministries such as ‘public works, health, and education’ were organised on a relatively small scale in terms of administrative structure. However, as the duties and responsibilities of the newly established Turkish Republic expanded over time with modernisation and economic development, the public bureaucracy also expanded accordingly (Eryılmaz, 2012: 296). In this context, the number of civil servants, which was 137.538 in 1910, rose to 104.115 in 1931, 134.779 in 1938, and 222.166 in 1946 (Gülmez, 1973: 31-33). During this period, education policies in particular were rapidly modernised. Village Institutes were established, teacher training colleges were expanded, and there was a significant increase in literacy rates (Fischer, 1979: 102).

One of the elements the newly established Republic of Türkiye used to introduce its reforms to the public was the Republican People's Party (Yalçındağ, 1970: 55). The party relied heavily on the bureaucracy of the Ministry of the Interior to implement the planned reforms, and the integration of the state and the party, which began in the 1930s, was further strengthened in 1936. The Minister of the Interior officially became the party's general secretary, and governors became the party's provincial chairmen. Civil administrators (governors and district governors) now performed political duties in addition to their administrative duties (Eryılmaz, 2012: 296). In the 1930s, following the lifting of customs-related conditions in Lausanne, the principle of statism was fully implemented, and with the direct involvement of the public sector in the country's economy, bureaucrats were now able to find positions for themselves in different cadres rather than solely in administrative positions. During this period, with the establishment of 19 economic state enterprises and the nationalisation of various institutions, bureaucrats began to be directly involved in economic and development activities as managers of industrial organisations.

The duties of bureaucrats during the Single Party Period expanded to an extent unseen even among bureaucrats of the Ottoman Empire. Instead of performing classic state functions such as maintaining public order and collecting taxes, as in the traditional Ottoman bureaucracy, bureaucrats during the Single Party Period gained the opportunity to participate directly in political processes alongside 'social, cultural, economic development and progress services' (Eryılmaz, 2012: 297). During the Atatürk and İnönü periods, the central state structure was strengthened, and an attempt was made to establish a 'rational bureaucracy' structure (Sakallıoğlu, 1996: 9).

The end of the Single Party Period after World War II marked a period in which the bureaucracy, which had attained extremely important positions and duties, began to lose these characteristics. Indeed, during World War II, the implementation of measures such as 'road tax' and 'animal tax' in Türkiye, which placed a considerable burden on the peasantry, the distribution of food and necessities and the implementation of price policies that granted privileges to civil servants in the midst of the war-induced crisis, and the fact that civil servants continued to look down on the people despite their efforts continued to look down on the public, leading to the bureaucracy losing its credibility in the eyes of the people (Yalçındağ, 1970: 56).

Once again, the powers and opportunities granted to civil servants led to an increase in their authority and influence over society, while society also contributed to the rise of negative perceptions of civil servants that had existed since the past. Towards the end of the 1930s, with the development of the private sector and the emergence of new professional groups, a decline in the share of civil servants' income began, and the golden age of civil servants came to an end (Eryılmaz, 2012: 297).

3.1.2. The Multi-Party Period (1946-1960)

With the establishment of the Democratic Party in 1946 and its election of members of parliament in the general elections, Türkiye officially and effectively transitioned from a single-party system to a multi-party system. The transition to a multi-party political system also affected the bureaucracy in Türkiye. With the Democratic Party coming to power, the effectiveness of the

bureaucracy first declined, and the bureaucracy began to face numerous obstacles. For the first time, a group that had been outside the traditional administration took power in political life, and a change occurred in the relationship between the bureaucracy and political power (Göküş, 2003: 41).

In 1946 and thereafter, i.e. after the transition to a multi-party system, modernisation efforts in public administration began with administrative reform reports (Barker, Neumark reports, etc.) (Demir, 2021: 64). Instead of a bureaucracy that was integrated with the ruling party and appeared to be a direct instrument of it, as was the case during the single-party era, a bureaucratic structure emerged that was subordinate to the political authority and had no ties to the opposition. Legal measures such as ‘taking over ministries,’ ‘forcing retirement,’ and ‘closing the Council of State route to government proceedings’ were taken by the Democratic Party government against high-level bureaucrats who had become integrated with the single-party regime (Şaylan, 1984: 305; Göküş, 2003: 42). During this period, the bureaucracy lost its influence in the country's administration. There was a decline in the power of bureaucrats in their strong positions within parliament and their solid ties with the political elite. In other words, there was a general decline in the ‘influence, prestige, status, and income’ of bureaucrats (Özbudun, 1995: 17; Göküş, 2003: 43).

In its 1946 party programme, the Democratic Party stated that ‘private enterprise and capital are fundamental to economic life, that state enterprises should exist without hindering private enterprise, and that certain enterprises established by the state may be transferred to the private sector (privatisation) provided that they are more profitable’. As can be understood from these statements, the Democratic Party was a party that pursued liberal policies. During this period, the private sector was encouraged, but statism did not completely end, and in this context, 13 new public economic enterprises were established. This situation began to increase the difference between the classical functional public bureaucracy and the economic functional bureaucracy. The economically functional bureaucracy was organised at the regional level, outside the control of the classical bureaucracy, and gained the opportunity to organise at the regional level as a new tier. Those working in the economically functional bureaucracy attained a more distinct and superior position in terms of social opportunities and status compared to others (Eryılmaz, 2012: 298-299). During this period, it was not possible for the bureaucracy to adapt to new environmental conditions and undergo transformation due to the political power of the Democratic Party and the associated policy changes.

There was a struggle between this party and the bureaucracy, which did not want to lose its previous dominant position. The Democratic Party, which was more sensitive to local interests and demands, did not respond to the wishes of the ruling elite. The bureaucracy reacted to the political power's views on the market economy and its behaviour regarding Atatürk's reforms (Eryılmaz, 2012: 298).

Another important development in the evolution of the bureaucracy in Türkiye in the 1950s was the reports prepared mainly by foreign experts, which explained Türkiye's development and progress through administrative changes that could be achieved through management systems. Although the first report to pioneer reforms in public administration during the republican period was the ‘Dorr Report’ prepared in 1933, the most prominent foreign expert reports prepared in the 1950s

were the ‘Neumark Report, Barker Report, Martin-Cush Report, Gruber Report, Baade Report, and Chailloux-Dantel Report’ (Özer, 2022: 71). The Neumark Report, prepared in 1949 by Prof. Dr. Fritz Neumark under the title ‘Report on the Principles of Rational Work in State Departments and Institutions,’ was the first administrative reform study.

According to this report, ‘while drawing attention to the problems experienced by the Turkish personnel system, recommendations were made to strengthen the inspection system, prevent personnel from accumulating in certain positions, strengthen the salary system, and eliminate unnecessary personnel expenses, while also emphasising the sluggishness of the work being carried out’ (Özer, 2022: 71). In a report prepared by J.M. Barker in 1951, issues such as "the inadequacy of trained personnel, the inadequacy of administrative organisation, the inadequacy of the appointment system, the inability to determine their duties, and the reduction of civil servants' purchasing power were mentioned, and alongside this, recommendations were made such as “reviewing personnel management, establishing a central personnel organisation, implementing a career system in the public sector, keeping personnel out of politics, and training personnel in agriculture, education, and health” (Öktem, 1992: 88). Similarly, the J. W. Martin-F.C.E Cush Report prepared in the same year included recommendations such as ‘increasing the number and quality of talented civil servants for efficient work, establishing a personnel department, enacting laws classifying public services, implementing a fair salary system, and not neglecting the morale of personnel’ (Öktem, 1992: 88-89).

The L. Gruber Report, prepared in 1951, made recommendations on ‘the legal status of central government and municipal personnel, the wage system, the preservation of purchasing power, working hours, and the limitation of the number of civil servants’ (Öktem, 1992: 89). The Baade and Chailloux-Dantel Reports focused on ‘personnel issues,’ while the Chailloux Report addressed the broader topics of ‘agriculture and tourism’ (Özer, 2022: 72). As stated in the Martin-Cush, Barker, and Gruber Reports, the proposal to establish a central personnel department was realised in 1960 with the establishment of the ‘State Personnel Department’ (Öktem, 1992: 91). In line with these recommendations, the Turkish and Middle Eastern Institute of Public Administration (TODAİE) was established in 1953, and the Department of Public Administration at Ankara University's Faculty of Political Sciences was established in 1957 (Özer, 2022:72).

Although efforts were made to implement reforms in Türkiye until 1960, these reforms did not achieve the desired results. There are three main reasons for this situation (TODAİE, 1970: 19 cited in Özer and Önen, 2019: 273):

- The institutions responsible for implementing the reforms did not give the necessary attention to their quality and scope;
- The necessary investigations were not carried out regarding the recruitment of qualified personnel to perform public service;
- The creation of the necessary environment for the success of the reforms was neglected.

3.1.3. The Period Between 1960 and 1982

In the process leading up to the 1960 military coup, which has been described as ‘the revenge of the bureaucracy,’ the influence of the bureaucracy, which had lost its power in the period before the coup, should not be forgotten. Indeed, one of the paths leading to the 1960 military coup was the defeat of the bureaucracy in the power struggle between the bureaucracy and politics. The bureaucracy, whose authority and power had diminished compared to the past and which sought to return to its former glory, sympathised with the 27 May 1960 military coup (Eryılmaz, 2012: 299). Before the coup, military personnel, who saw themselves as protectors and guardians of the state, joined forces with the civil bureaucracy and intellectuals to criticise the political establishment (Özer, 2022: 73). With the coup, the military, who thought that politics had taken precedence over bureaucracy during the Democratic Party era, took over the government and wanted to bring back their old power in political life.

The 1961 the Constitution of the Turkish Republic brought in important changes so that the bureaucracy could get back the power it had lost during the Democratic Party era. In a sense, it can be said that the bureaucracy, which played a role in the coup, was rewarded for its efforts. With this constitution, the use of popular sovereignty was no longer limited to parliament as the sole organ, but was now exercised through the organs mentioned in the constitution (1961 Constitution, Article 57), and steps were taken to establish new autonomous institutions and increase the autonomy of existing institutions. An important feature of these institutions is that the personnel who established or managed them were bureaucrats or had previously been bureaucrats (Yalçındağ, 1970: 57). Before the coup, military personnel, who saw themselves as protectors and guardians of the state, joined forces with the civil bureaucracy and intellectuals to criticise the political establishment (Özer, 2022:73). With the coup, the military, who thought that politics had taken precedence over bureaucracy during the Democratic Party era, took over the government and wanted to bring back their old power in political life.

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The 1961 the Constitution of the Turkish Republic, drafted by the military, provided for judicial review of laws by the Constitutional Court, the strengthening of administrative justice to exercise oversight over the executive branch, the right of civil servants to appeal to the Council of State, and the establishment of the Council of Judges and Prosecutors as examples of this situation (Özer, 2022:73).

While it can be said that the power of the bureaucracy increased relatively after 1961, the reforms implemented also contributed to this situation. However, with the establishment of the ‘State Planning Organisation,’ a technical institution, in 1961, the group of technocrats trained in this institution strengthened their power over the political authority by using their knowledge and expertise in the bureaucracy and political authority. The technical nature of the economy bureaucracy increased the need for technocrats and their influence on the determination of public policies (Eryılmaz, 2012: 299). With the transition to the planned development period, the first comprehensive reform effort in public administration began with the Central Government Organisation Research Project (MEHTAP) prepared in 1963. This project was prepared with the aim of redefining the distribution of duties, personnel system, organisational structure and financial control mechanisms of the central administration.

In the following years, the 1971 report on Principles and Recommendations for Administrative Reform (İYD) aimed to update the MEHTAP findings and develop feasible strategies. In the 1990s, which can be considered a continuation of these reports, the Public Administration Research Project (KAYA) aimed to contribute to the modernisation of public administration by presenting reform proposals that included more comprehensive, systematic, and structural analyses (Kaya, 2016: 176).

The 1961 the Constitution of the Turkish Republic granted public employees the right to form unions, expanded the scope of the Council of State's supervisory authority over the actions and transactions of the executive branch, provided scientific and administrative autonomy to universities, and granted teaching staff the right to join political parties, thereby increasing the power of the bureaucracy vis-à-vis the political authority (Eryılmaz, 2012: 299). Another development during this period was the strengthening of the military bureaucracy. The 1961 the Constitution of the Turkish Republic enabled the military bureaucracy to assume an influential and more autonomous position in state administration through the ‘National Security Council’ and eliminated the distinction between the areas of responsibility of the military and civil bureaucracies. Now, there were two distinct bureaucratic structures, each with its own unique system: the civilian administrative system on one side and the military administrative system on the other (Eryılmaz, 2012: 299).

From a bureaucratic perspective, all these developments have not been sufficient to restore the influential position of bureaucrats during the Single Party Period. Studies conducted between 1960 and 1982 to measure the social status of civil servants show that the living conditions of bureaucrats have deteriorated. Unlike before, bureaucrats have lost their status as the most affluent, enviable segment of society with access to consumer goods. The financial resources of bureaucrats and their share of national income have declined in the face of high price increases (Us, 1973: 73). Even after the enactment of the Civil Servants Law No. 657 of 1965 and Law No. 1327 of 1970, the salary levels of civil servants remained inadequate, strengthening their tendency to switch to freelance professions, and civil servants lost their prestige in society as well as in their own eyes (Us, 1973: 73).

During the period between 1960 and 1982, some legal regulations targeting the bureaucracy were implemented, which remain valid to this day. Firstly, in the 1961 the Constitution of the Turkish

Republic, the scope of provisions relating to civil servants was expanded compared to the 1924 the Constitution of the Turkish Republic, and with the amendments made, provisions were introduced regarding civil servants' 'conditions for participating in elections, duties to be performed, legal regulations regarding their personal affairs, and prohibition of discrimination between members of political parties and trade unions and other citizens.' (Articles 68, 69, 117, 118, and 119). The Civil Servants Law No. 657 of 1965, which is still in force today and for which no new law has yet been prepared, was also enacted during this period. This law, which was a continuation of the reform efforts that began in the 1950s, was prepared with a lack of knowledge, expertise, and experience, did not address organisational and management issues, failed to establish a service relationship with civil servants, considered only the issue of wages, and did not take public opinion into account during its preparation (Öktem, 1992: 96). The law was based on the principles of classification, career, and competence, and included various issues such as basic principles regarding civil servants, forms of employment, duties and responsibilities, transfers, working hours, and the termination of civil servants. On the other hand, with the enactment of Law No. 1327 in 1970, approximately 55% of the provisions of the original Law No. 657 were amended, and with subsequent legal regulations (laws, decrees with the force of law, etc.), it has almost lost its original form (Öktem, 1992: 96). While the collective bargaining system implemented in 1963 brought about a relative improvement in the financial rights of workers, civil servants were unable to achieve any progress in their status because they did not have the right to collective bargaining, and they remained in the status of workers until 1980 (Öktem, 1992:97).

Between 1960 and 1982, the inability to create sufficient employment opportunities to address issues such as population growth, urban sprawl, unemployment, and increasing population led to the use of civil service positions to prevent unemployment, which in turn led to an increase in the number of civil servants (Öktem, 1992: 95). In this context, the number of civil servants rose to 449.869 in 1963, 655.737 in 1970, 962.537 in 1976, and 1.312.243 in 1980 (Çitçi, 1986: 42).

Another reason for this situation is that there were many coalition governments in Türkiye from the 1970s to the 1980s, and the parties that came to power during this period preferred a system of 'plunder and spoils' rather than meritocracy. Each party forming the coalition governments pursued a policy of patronage and favouritism, bringing their own party cadres into the bureaucracy (Özer, 2022: 73). In addition, following the military memorandum of 12 March 1970, changes were made to the constitution that strengthened the executive branch and took steps to remove the autonomy of the bureaucracy (Eryılmaz, 2012: 300).

EVALUATION AND CONCLUSION

The new Turkish Republic was established without completely erasing the Ottoman legacy, with a human resource pool consisting largely of the same bureaucrats. This situation led to certain traditions and behavioural patterns being inherited from the Ottoman Empire to the Turkish Republic. Indeed, the conservatism of bureaucratic organisations and their refusal to relinquish their authority are precisely manifestations of this situation. This is because the bureaucrats, who were the founders of the republic and the sole defenders of Atatürk's reforms, sought to preserve the centralised

approach they had adopted from the Ottoman Empire, excluding other social classes in order to consolidate their authority. From the 1930s onwards, they also assumed a position of economic control. Bureaucrats, who were already involved in politics, found their place in politics legally with the 1936 reform. After that, the bureaucracy became an important actor and implementer of the policies of the party state.

The privileged status of bureaucrats, which had already been declining in the eyes of the public due to the privileges they had created for themselves during World War II, was further diminished with the rise of the Democratic Party, as the founding class of the republic was pushed out of the system. With the Democratic Party, it was desired that bureaucrats occupy a natural position rather than being integrated into the state party. The 1950s were also years when Turkish bureaucracy and public administration were shaped by reports such as the Neumark Report, the Barker Report, the Martin-Cush Report, and the Gruber Report. It would be appropriate to make the following observation here. The unquestioning approach that began with the Tanzimat, which did not take local elements into account and accepted the superiority of the West, was also evident in these reports. The fact that these reports, prepared in this vein, were drafted after the political formation that had been pushed outside the system throughout the history of the republic came to power actually shows that the understanding of the West's absolute superiority continued even during the Democratic Party's rule. Although the changes proposed in the reports were quite reasonable given the conditions of the time, it is unclear to what extent they reflected the actual situation in terms of the administrative approach in the territory of the Republic of Türkiye. This is because, rather than being prepared solely on the basis of observation, it would have been more appropriate to adopt an approach based on the practical shortcomings and practices of the Republic of Türkiye's system.

During the process leading up to the 1960 military coup, the military and civil bureaucracy, which had lost its power, supported the soldiers who carried out the coup in order to regain its former strength. The result of these efforts was reflected in the 1961 the Constitution of the Turkish Republic, which established various institutions within a constitutional framework. In addition, during this period, an institution such as the State Planning Organisation was established, which held technical power. As Weber emphasises in his theory, specialisation is a vital phenomenon in bureaucracy. However, it is also problematic when experts use the information at their disposal to influence politics in a bureaucratic manner. In this context, the establishment of the State Planning Organisation led to the transformation of the bureaucracy into a technocratic group that was not politically accountable, which was able to influence the country's politics and freely use the power of its knowledge without having to bear the political consequences. Since the 1960s, bureaucrats have been unable to regain the prestige they lost during the Democratic Party era, either in terms of status or financially. In addition, bureaucratic positions were used as a means of employment to solve the economic problems that increased in a partisan manner between 1970 and 1982. This led to the formation of cliques within the bureaucracy and resulted in relationships being established around political groups rather than a straightforward relationship between politics and bureaucracy, creating an obstacle to the rational functioning of the Turkish bureaucratic mechanism.

Çıkar Çatışması Beyanı

Yazar(lar), bu makalenin araştırma, yazarlık ve/veya yayın süreci ile ilgili herhangi bir potansiyel çıkar çatışması olmadığını beyan eder.

Mali Destek

Yazar(lar), bu makalenin araştırılması, yazılması ve/veya yayınlanması için herhangi bir mali destek almamıştır.

Yayın Etiği Beyanı

Çalışmada etik dışı bir husus bulunmadığını, araştırma ve yayın etiğine özenle uyulduğunu beyan ederiz.

Yazar Katkı Oranı

Çalışma, iki yazarlı olup yazarın katkı oranı %50'dir.

Etik Kurul İzni

Çalışma etik kurul izni gerektirmeyen çalışmalardandır.

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